

SPLenic ARTERY ANEURYSM RUPTURE : CASE REPORT

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Keywords

Rupture,

Shock,

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ABSTRACT

Visceral artery aneurysms are rare pathologies. In this , we present a 41-year-old male patient with splenic artery aneurysm rupture.

INTRODUCTION

Visceral artery aneurysms are rare pathologies. The splenic artery is most commonly involved (60%), followed by the hepatic artery (25%), then the superior mesenteric artery (5%). Early diagnosis and treatment is important because of its asymptomatic course and the possibility of rupture.¹

CASE

A 41-year-old male patient was brought to the emergency department with the complaint of sudden fainting while working in the field. He had no other comorbidities other than a known diagnosis of cirrhosis. In the initial evaluation; consciousness was clear, orientated, cooperative, neurological examination was normal, agitated appearance, cold sweats were present. Lung auscultation and abdominal examination were normal. Blood pressure was 60-40 mmHg, pulse 76/min, respiratory rate 20/min, SpO₂ 96%, ECG sinus rhythm. Melena and haematechesia were not detected in the rectal touch examination. In blood tests, White bloodcell count was 12.24×10^3 mcl, haemoglobin 7.9 g/dl (8.7 g/dl one day before), platelet count 139×10^3 /ml, blood gaspH: 7.42, pCO₂: 27, HCO₃: 17.5, AST: 59 U/l, ALT: 39U/l, GGT: 99U/l, total bilirubin: 1.7mg/dl, lipase 57 U/l, electrolyt evalues and rena lfunctions were normal, hs-Troponin: 0.12ng/ml. Control haemogram and hs-troponin tests showed haemoglobin 6.6 and hs-troponin 0.39. No change was found in the control ECG. Echocardiography in the emergency department revealed normal heart Wall motion, normal heart valves and no pericardial effusion. CT scan of the brain and thorax showed no urgent pathological findings. Abdominal CT scan showed a hyperdense appearance compatible with an aneurysm with a diameter of approximately 2.5 cm in the distal part of the splenic artery. The patient was evaluated as splenic artery aneurysm rupture and taken to emergency surgery by general surgery.

DISCUSSION

Splenic artery aneurysms are more common in the 5th and 6th decade but can be seen in all age groups. The incidence is 4 times higher in women than in men. They are usually single and saccular and located in the mid-distal part of the splenic artery. The etiology includes atherosclerosis, focal arterial inflammation, pancreatitis, hypersplenism, portal hypertension, liver transplantation, trauma and pregnancy. In the present case, the patient had a history of cirrhosis,

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which explains the etiology of portal hypertension and splenic artery aneurysm.^{1,2}

Splenic artery aneurysms are 80% asymptomatic. The risk of rupture is increased in aneurysms larger than 2 cm, symptomatic, with a history of transplantation, inflammatory aneurysms and in women of child bearing age and pregnant women. Symptom such as left upper quadrant pain, nausea and vomiting may be observed. Apart from splenic infarction which is rare, the most important complication is rupture (3-10%). The mortality rate of rupture characterised by sudden abdominal pain, hypotension and shock is 70%. In the case we presented, the patient presented with shock, abdominal pain was absent, abdominal examination was comfortable, a differential diagnosis of shock was made and a definitive diagnosis was made with abdominal CT imaging.³⁻⁵

CONCLUSION

The differential diagnosis of patients presenting with shock should be made well and rare cases such as splenic artery aneurysm rupture should be considered.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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